

Face Mask Ventilation Quality and Its Association with Opioid Dose and Neuromuscular Blockade During Anaesthesia Induction for Tracheal Intubation

A protocol for a retrospective cohort study

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Introduction

Approximately one million people undergo surgery worldwide each day, the majority under general anaesthesia, emphasising the importance of safe airway management^{1,2}. Face mask ventilation (FMV) is a fundamental component of anaesthesia. It enables oxygenation when spontaneous respiration is insufficient and serves as a bridge for oxygenation until a definitive airway, such as a tracheal tube or a supraglottic airway, is secured. It may also function as a rescue technique in the event of difficult airway management³. FMV is also routinely used as the primary airway strategy for brief procedures in low-risk patients.

Despite being a standard procedure, FMV can be challenging. Difficult mask ventilation (DMV) is an infrequent but clinically consequential event, reported in approximately 1.1-6.1% of patients⁴⁻⁷. When DMV occurs, it is associated with adverse events, including hypoxia, which remains the leading cause of airway-related mortality⁸. Effective and reliable FMV is critical in mitigating this risk⁹. The Quality of FMV has traditionally been defined using the Han scale¹⁰. Accurate preoperative identification of patients at risk of DMV is essential, as it enables appropriate allocation of resources and may reduce the risk of morbidity and mortality⁶. Identified risk factors include advanced age, increased body mass index (BMI), and prior neck radiation; however, reliable preoperative prediction remains challenging^{6,11}.

Neuromuscular blocking agents (NMBAs) are recommended in current airway management guidelines to achieve optimal intubating conditions in both children and adults^{12,13}. Between anaesthesia induction and tracheal intubation, FMV is advised to maintain continuous oxygen flow and to facilitate carbon dioxide elimination¹². The choice of pharmacological induction strategy may influence the quality of FMV. Randomised clinical trials have reported improved quality of FMV following NMBA administration¹⁴⁻¹⁶. However, these studies were primarily conducted in selected populations of healthy patients, potentially limiting generalisability. Moreover, NMBA use is associated with a risk of adverse events¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Although current guidelines recommend administration of an NMBA before FMV is attempted when tracheal intubation is planned¹², the association between NMBAs and the quality of FMV has not been evaluated in a large population-based cohort.

NMBA use represents only one of several possible pharmacological strategies for airway management, and opioids are the most commonly used alternative²⁰. A recent Scandinavian survey reports

that nearly half of Danish anaesthesiologists prefer remifentanyl without NMBAs for non-acute intubations²¹. Intubation conditions achieved with remifentanyl are at best comparable to those obtained with NMBAs^{22–24}. Opioids may influence upper airway tone and chest wall rigidity, potentially influencing the quality of FMV²⁵. Despite widespread use, the effect of opioids on FMV and DMV outcomes remains poorly characterised.

Objective

The aim of this study is to evaluate the quality of FMV during opioid-supplemented induction compared with NMBA-supplemented inductions.

We hypothesise that the use of NMBAs is associated with more favourable conditions for FMV compared to using high-dose opioid strategies at induction.

Methods

This protocol is developed for reporting in accordance with The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE)²⁶.

Study design

A retrospective cohort study based on prospectively collected clinical data on patients undergoing general anaesthesia with tracheal intubation.

Data collection

Data are extracted from the electronic health record (EHR) system Sundhedsplatformen (Epic Systems Corporation, WI, USA) and validated and cleaned via the TRIPLE-A database²⁷. The database covers all anaesthesia-linked surgical procedures performed at public hospitals in the Capital and Zealand Regions between 1 January 2017 and 30 June 2025 accounting for approximately 1.2 million anaesthetic procedures. Clinical data in TRIPLE A were not collected or registered for research purposes; they were prospectively documented as part of routine care and will subsequently be extracted for retrospective analysis.

We will be able to identify patients undergoing multiple anaesthetic procedures requiring FMV through unique pseudonymised patient IDs. Only the first recorded case per patient will be included

in the analysis to ensure independence of observations and avoid bias from repeated measurements within individuals.

The project was deemed exempt for ethical approval by the Regional Research Ethics Committee (R-26012045, 17 February 2026). Data extraction and the project was approved by Centre for Health, Capital Region, Team for Medical Records Research (R-26012045, 17 February 2026). Finally, the project was approved by The Capital Region Legal Department (p-2026-21227, 10 April 2026).

Data handling

Data will be anonymised prior to analysis to ensure patient confidentiality and compliance with data protection regulations.

The dataset will undergo preprocessing and validation before analysis, including checks for missing values, duplicates, and errors. Only validated data will be used in the analysis to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Variables will be coded according to predefined definitions. Continuous variables will be categorised using clinically relevant thresholds where appropriate. Derived variables will be constructed to enhance clinical interpretability, including composite outcomes, severity classifications, and exposure groupings based on opioid dosing and NMBA administration.

Data will be stored in the secure TRIPLE-A database with restricted access.

Setting and population

The cohort comprises patients treated in public hospitals in the Capital and Zealand Regions of Denmark.

For the present study, data will be extracted from 1 January 2020 to 30 June 2025, comprising approximately 400,000 anaesthetic procedures, in accordance with predefined data access limitations.

Inclusion criteria

Patients are eligible for inclusion if:

- 18 years of age or above
- Undergoing tracheal intubation with attempted FMV

Exclusion criteria

Patients are excluded if:

- Inhalational anaesthesia during induction
- Rapid sequence induction
- Incomplete case time log (missing data on time of induction)
- Missing weight and height data

Outcomes and exposures

Primary outcome

- Incidence of difficult or impossible (Han grade 3-4) mask ventilation¹⁰, as assessed by the anaesthesia provider and registered in the EHR

Exploratory outcomes

- Serious complications
 - o All-cause mortality within 30 days
 - o Admission to intensive care unit (ICU) within 30 days
 - o Readmission within 30 days
- Pulmonary complications
 - o Pulmonary aspiration of gastric contents
 - o Pneumonia within seven postoperative days
- Hypoxaemia: defined as oxygen saturation <80%
- Hypotension: defined as mean arterial pressure (MAP) <50mmHg
- Bradycardia: defined as heart rate <35beats/min

As patients undergoing cardiac or neurosurgery are frequently admitted directly to the ICU as part of routine postoperative care, these patients were excluded from analyses of the ICU admission component of the serious complications outcome.

Primary exposure

- Use of NMBA and opioids (no/low-dose, intermediate-dose or high-dose) at anaesthesia induction. Categories are:
 - NMBA use (regardless of opioid dose)
 - No/low-dose opioids without NMBA
 - Intermediate-dose opioids without NMBA
 - High-dose opioids without NMBA

Each patient is assigned to a single, mutually exclusive exposure group based on medication during induction. Detailed definitions of opioid dose categories are provided in the Appendix.

Covariates

The following variables will be included as covariates and adjusted for in the multivariable regression analyses.

Patient related

- Age
- American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status classification (1, 2, 3, 4, 5)
- BMI
- Sex (Female/Male)
- Ability to protrude lower jaw (Y/N)
- Limited mouth opening (Y/N)
- Limited neck extension (Y/N)
- Mallampati classification (I, II, III, IV)
- Short thyromental distance (Y/N)
- Prior oral/pharyngeal/laryngeal cancer (Y/N)
- Previous difficult airway (Y/N)
- Sleep apnoea (Y/N)

Organisational

- Site (Hospital)
- Operator (Anaesthesiologist, Anaesthesiologist in training, Anaesthetic nurse, Trainee anaesthetic nurse)

- Timing of procedure (Normal hours/Shift hours)

Baseline variables

A detailed list of variable definitions is provided in **Appendix 1**.

Statistical analysis

Baseline data will be presented using descriptive statistics. Categorical variables will be represented as counts and percentages.

A multivariable logistic regression model adjusted for covariates specified below will be used to assess the primary outcome of difficult mask ventilation and other dichotomous outcomes. The results will be presented as odds ratios (OR) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals. Outcome definitions were informed by the Airway Management Outcome Measures (ATOM) core outcome set²⁸, and applied as closely as possible given the available registry data. We will use a forced-entry approach for our multivariable analyses. Thus, all multivariable models will include the protocol-specified exposure and a priori-selected covariates based on clinical relevance and without univariable selection. Univariable analyses will be performed for descriptive purposes only and to comply with STROBE reporting recommendations.

In addition to conventional logistic regression models, potential non-linear associations between opioid doses and outcomes will be assessed using logistic regression models incorporating restricted cubic splines. Knots will be placed at the 5th, 35th, 65th, and 95th percentiles of the exposure distribution, measured as opioid dose ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) during induction, for patients not receiving an NMBA. These models will include the same prespecified covariates as the primary analyses.

The following variables will be included as adjustment variables in all analyses. Patient-related covariates include age, sex, BMI, ASA classification, sleep apnoea, prior oral/pharyngeal/laryngeal cancer, ability to protrude the lower jaw, limited mouth opening, limited neck extension, Mallampati classification, short thyromental distance, and previous difficult airway. Organisational covariates include site, operator category, and procedural timing.

Missing data will be assessed for all variables. If a complete-case analysis would exclude more than 10% of participants due to missing data, multiple imputation will be performed. Missingness will be imputed for covariates with less than 40% missingness. Variables with more than 40% missingness

will be excluded from the analysis. Imputation models will include difficulty of mask ventilation, age, sex, BMI, ASA classification, sleep apnoea, prior oral/pharyngeal/laryngeal cancer, ability to protrude the lower jaw, limited mouth opening, limited neck extension, Mallampati classification, short thyromental distance, previous difficult airway, site, operator category, and procedural timing. Twenty imputed datasets will be generated, and estimates will be combined using Rubin's rules.

For all analyses, we will present statistical tests as two-sided and consider a p-value less than 0.05 statistically significant.

Analyses of exploratory outcomes will be considered hypothesis-generating, given the increased risk of Type I error when performing multiple testing. Composite outcomes will be compared using the win ratio method, with the hierarchy defined above, and with pairwise comparisons performed between each opioid group and the NMBA group. Variables used in the analyses will undergo systematic data validation, including manual review of at least 40 randomly selected records per variable. Any identified discrepancies will be corrected, and the process will be repeated iteratively until no further inconsistencies are detected. Statistical analyses will be performed using latest available stable version of R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

Sensitivity analyses will be conducted comparing results from complete case analyses and analyses based on multiple imputation to assess the robustness of findings.

Appendix

Appendix 1: Variable table

Variable	Measurement	Definition	When
Primary outcome			
Difficult or impossible mask ventilation	Dichotomous (Y/N)	FMV during induction classified as difficult (Han grade 3) or impossible (Han grade 4) by the anaesthesia provider, according to standard Han grading criteria and recorded in the EHR. Cases with Han grade 1 or 2 were graded as not difficult	Prior to (attempts of) tracheal intubation
Exploratory outcomes			
Serious complications	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Composite outcome defined as any of the following: death, ICU admission, or hospital readmission	Within 30 postoperative days
Pulmonary complications	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Composite outcome defined as pulmonary aspiration or pneumonia	During airway management for aspiration; within 7 postoperative days for pneumonia
Hypoxaemia	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Hypoxaemia is defined as oxygen saturation <80%	From start of induction and the following 20 minutes
Hypotension	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Hypotension is defined as MAP <50mmHg	From start of induction and the following 20 minutes

Bradycardia	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Bradycardia is defined as heart rate <35 beats/min	From start of induction and the following 20 minutes
Primary exposure			
Pharmacological agent at induction	Categorical (NMBA yes, No/low dose opioids, intermediate dose opioids, high dose opioids)	<p>Pharmacological airway management at induction was defined as a composite exposure based on NMBA use (yes/no) and opioid dose (No/low vs intermediate/high), yielding four mutually exclusive groups. Patients receiving an NMBA were classified in the NMBA group irrespective of concomitant opioid administration.</p> <p>The weight used in calculations will be the lowest of actual body weight and ideal body weight (IBW). IBW is calculated as height (cm) minus 105 for women and height (cm) minus 100 for men. Values <40 kg for either IBW or actual body weight will be considered implausible; where available, the alternative weight measure will be used.</p> <p>High dose opioid: defined as a dosis of sufentanil $\geq 0.4\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, remifentanil $\geq 4\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, fentanyl $\geq 4\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, alfentanil $\geq 40\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$,</p> <p>Intermediate dose opioid: defined as a dosis of sufentanil ≥ 0.2 and <0.4</p>	At time of induction

		<p>$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, remifentanyl ≥ 2 and $< 4 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, fentanyl ≥ 2 and $< 4 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, or alfentanil ≥ 20 and $< 40 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.</p> <p>Low dose opioid: defined as doses $< 2 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for remifentanyl, $< 20 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for alfentanil, $< 2 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for fentanyl, and $< 0.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ for sufentanyl, or no opioid administration.</p> <p>For patients > 70 years old, all opioid dose thresholds are reduced by 50%.</p> <p>Dose thresholds were defined a priori based on clinical practice and relative opioid potency, aiming to reflect clinically meaningful differences in opioid effect during induction²⁹⁻³¹. Thresholds were harmonised across agents to approximate comparable effect on FMV</p>	
Exposure for cubic spline models			
Opioid dose during induction, expressed as remifentanyl-equivalent dose ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Continuous	A continuous exposure variable will be defined as total opioid exposure during induction expressed as remifentanyl-equivalent dose ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$). Conversion factors were derived from the previously defined high-dose thresholds. This results in a relative potency scale where fentanyl and remifentanyl are	At time of induction

		<p>considered equipotent, sufentanil is assigned a 10-fold higher potency, and alfentanil a 10-fold lower potency.</p> <p>The weight used in calculations will be the lowest of actual body weight and ideal body weight (IBW). IBW is calculated as height (cm) minus 105 for women and height (cm) minus 100 for men. Values <40 kg for either IBW or actual body weight will be considered implausible; where available, the alternative weight measure will be used.</p> <p>For patients >70 years old, the calculated remifentanil equivalent dose was multiplied by two; for example, an administered dose of 2 µg/kg was analysed as 4 µg/kg</p>	
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Covariates			
Age	Continuous	Age at time of surgery	At surgery
ASA	Categorical (1, 2, 3, 4, 5)	Preoperative physical status according to ASA	Pre-anaesthetic assessment
BMI	Continuous	Body mass index, calculated as weight (kg) divided by height (m) squared	Last available registration before surgery
Sex	Dichotomous (Female/Male)	Biological sex	NA

Ability to protrude lower jaw	Dichotomous (Y/N)	The capacity to bring the lower incisors in front of the upper incisors	Assessed during pre-anaesthetic interview
Limited mouth opening	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Classified as short if the distance between the upper and lower incisors at maximal mouth opening, or the intergingival distance in edentulous patients is <4cm	Assessed during pre-anaesthetic interview
Limited neck extension	Dichotomous (Y/N)	The range of motion from full extension through full flexion	Assessed during pre-anaesthetic interview
Mallampati classification	Categorical (I, II, III, IV)	The visibility of the oropharyngeal structures is assessed on the patient sitting in neutral position with maximum mouth opening and tongue protrusion without phonation	Assessed during pre-anaesthetic interview
Short thyromental distance	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Classified as short if the measured distance between the mentum and the thyroid notch with the neck fully extended is <6.5 cm or 3 finger widths	Assessed during pre-anaesthetic interview
Prior oral/pharyngeal/laryngeal cancer	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Previous diagnosis of an oral, pharyngeal or laryngeal cancer through ICD10 codes	At time of induction
Previous difficult airway	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Previous difficult airway, classified as a registration of DMV or difficult tracheal intubation in relation to previous anaesthesias	Assessed during pre-anaesthetic interview
Sleep apnoea	Dichotomous (Y/N)	Has the patient been diagnosed with sleep apnoea	At time of induction

Site	Categorical (A-G)	The hospital at which the procedure was performed	At time of induction
Operator	Categorical (anaesthesiologist, anaesthesiologist in training, anaesthetic nurse, trainee anaesthetic nurse)	Occupation and experience of FMV provider	At time of induction
Timing of procedure	Dichotomous (Normal hours/Shift hours)	Timing of procedure was categorised as normal hours (07:00–14:59) or shift hours (15:00–06:59) on weekdays, with all procedures performed on weekends (Saturday and Sunday) classified as shift hours	Anaesthesia event start time
Baseline variables			
Type of laryngoscopy	Dichotomous (Direct laryngoscopy/Video laryngoscopy)	Laryngoscopy technique used for endotracheal intubation	During airway management
Type of NMBA for induction	Dichotomous (non-depolarising vs depolarising NMBA)	The NMBA administered during induction	At time of induction
Type of opioid used during induction	Categorical (remifentanyl, alfentanyl, fentanyl, sufentanyl)	The opioid administered during induction	At time of induction

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